

LOCAL FAILURE PROCESSES IN FIBER REINFORCED POLYMERS

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SUMMARY

The breakage of a fiber and its effect on the strain energy is studied in a model composite, this is, a single fiber embedded in a dogbone specimen. The fracture process is recorded by an acoustic emission device, the crack patterns are monitored under a microscope. A finite element analysis is performed in order to estimate the energy released by different failure scenarios. The abilities and limitations of the acoustic emission analysis in characterizing different failure types in fiber reinforced composites are evaluated.

Keywords: fiber, interface, composite material, failure, acoustic emission, fracture mechanics, energy release rate, finite element analysis

INTRODUCTION

In fiber reinforced composites global failure usually is initiated by local failure processes, either by fiber breakage, matrix cracking or interface failure or, obviously, by a combination of these elementary failure processes. The processes differ by the amount of energy released [1,2] as well as by the process time. The fiber fracture is a highly dynamical process since the crack propagates unstable and the crack velocity in glass is high [3]. Due to the high Young's modulus of the fibers, a large amount of energy is stored in the fiber which is released by the crack. Matrix and interface cracks can propagate stable or unstable, depending on the specific local conditions. Even though the amount of energy released by a matrix crack is of similar magnitude as a fiber crack of same length, its energy release rate is much lower in comparison to the fiber break due to the larger area of the matrix crack. Different failure scenarios are investigated in this paper, this is, fiber cracks accompanied by matrix or interface cracks of different lengths. A direct optical observation of the fracture process, however, is not very promising due to the dimensions as well as due to the high speed of the process. The acoustic emission analysis offers a chance to get some insight into these rapid microscopical processes.

ACOUSTIC EMISSION ANALYSIS

The different elementary failure processes are characterized by using the acoustic emission analysis. We want to figure out whether the amplitude distribution as well as the frequency spectra allow a discrimination of the respective failure processes. One should, however, be aware of the fact that the acoustic emission analysis cannot observe the fracture process directly but can only observe the effect the fracture process exerts on

the specimen. With other words, the mechanical wave initiated by the fiber breakage is monitored. In addition, the acoustic emission analysis itself has strong limitations in that the sensor is not an objective measuring instrument but it is another mechanical system, which responds to a mechanical excitation with a characteristic motion. As a result, the electrical signal generated by the sensor is a superimposition of the mechanical signal of the specimen and the characteristics of the sensor. A further component which has to be kept in mind is the electronics behind the sensor, which again superimposes its own characteristics on the electrical signal. In consequence, the signal measured by the acoustic emission device is an intensely modified mapping of the original source.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The fracture of a fiber is studied using a simple model composite. A single fiber is embedded in a typical dogbone specimen with a length of 100mm and 5x5mm in width. The length of the straight part is 60mm. The fibers are unsized E-glass fibers with a diameter of 80 μ m. The matrix is an epoxy resin (EpoFix made by Struers). The experiments are performed on a mini tensile machine which is mounted under a microscope. The specimen is loaded under fixed grips conditions, this is, displacement controlled. The acoustic emission signals are recorded by a 4 channel 14Bit converter board with a sampling rate up to $50 \cdot 10^6$ samples/second and an input range up to 2V. Three acoustic emission sensors (Pico sensors made by Physical Acoustics) are mounted on the front side of the specimen in order to allow optical monitoring. The distance between neighbouring sensors is 25mm. The numbering starts on the left hand side (fig. 1).

Fig. 1: sketch of fiber fracture specimen

FIBER FRACTURE

First we analyse the consequences of a fiber breakage in the model composite. The breakage leads to an abrupt decrease of the stiffness resulting in an abrupt unloading of the specimen. Even though the effect of one fiber break is very small for the specimen in total, it is dramatic in the vicinity of the fiber break. The region around the fiber break is intensely unloaded, except of the crack tips. The amount of energy released is several times higher than the energy necessary to form the crack faces. A part of the released energy is transformed into kinetic energy in form of a mechanical wave traveling through the specimen. Since the stresses in the zone around the circular crack tip are strongly increased (figs. 2a-c), some part of the released energy is absorbed here.

Before we study the wave initiated by the crack we take a look at the process of fiber cracking. The fracture of the fiber starts at a local fault at the fiber surface. Then the crack propagates to the center of the fiber as well as in circumferential direction. However, we will not study the process of a fiber fracture in detail in this paper but rather

use an idealized model, assuming an axisymmetrical crack starting at a circumferential fault.

In fracture mechanics we are used to the conception that a mode I crack results in an opening of the crack faces. If we transfer this to the fiber crack, assuming the crack running from the surface to the center of the fiber, it follows that the circular crack faces have to draw back. If the fiber is assumed to be perfectly bonded to the matrix, no opening of the crack could arise. Accordingly, if actually a crack forms on the fiber surface, either a radial matrix crack must develop or a debonding of the fiber end. Both phenomena are encountered in microscopical investigations of fiber fractures (figs. 3a,b).

Figure 2a: shear stresses - fiber break
without matrix crack with matrix crack

Figure 2b: Mises stresses - fiber break
without matrix crack with matrix crack

Finite element solutions of the stress field using an axisymmetrical model show high shear stress concentrations in case of a (hypothetical) pure fiber break (fig. 2a). The center of the fiber is on the left edge, the crack is seen on the bottom of the plots. In case of a simultaneous radial matrix crack the shear stresses in the interface remain still very high and, as a matter of course, stress concentrations of same order develop at the crack tip. The Mises stresses show how the stressed zone moves with the crack tip (fig. 2b).

WAVES CAUSED BY FIBER BREAKAGE

No we come back to the wave caused by the fiber break. In order to get some idea what happens after the fiber break, first we take a look at a very simple model. We assume a single rod which is not embedded in any other material and which breaks over the whole cross section in one instant. The crack forms two fiber ends which are, without question, unloaded. The event generating the wave therefore is the sudden unloading of the respective cross sections forming the new crack faces. The unloading simply is the

inverse problem of an impact load on the end of the rod. With the impact, two phenomena develop. The hit surface starts to move in the direction of the impact load and this motion propagates along the rod with the longitudinal wave velocity, owing to the one-dimensional wave equation

$$c_L \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} \quad \text{with} \quad c_L = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda + 2\mu}{\rho}} \quad \text{or even simpler} \quad c_L = \sqrt{\frac{E}{\rho}}$$

The situation in the three-dimensional model composite is far more complex. At first, the cross section does not crack in one instant but the crack runs from the surface to the center of the fiber. That is, we do not simply have a longitudinal wave in the fiber but also a shear component. We are confronted with the three-dimensional wave equation, this is, the Navier equation of motion:

$$\mu \Delta \mathbf{u} + (\lambda + \mu) \text{grad div } \mathbf{u} = \rho \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{u}}{\partial t^2}$$

This vector equation for the displacement field is a coupled differential equation of second order in the displacement vector as well as in time. The equation usually is split in two simpler equations by applying the Helmholtz decomposition, this is, the decomposition of the displacement field in a rotational-free part and a divergence-free part. In doing so, we obtain one equation for the longitudinal and another one for the shear wave. In order to calculate the total displacement field we had to find a solution not only for one material but for the fiber and the matrix as well. It is evident that an analytical solution even for the simple model composite under consideration is not possible in general.

The shear component, however, which is caused in the matrix as a result of the retraction of the fiber as well as due to the simultaneous matrix or interface crack, is much more important than the shear wave in the fiber, mentioned above. In total, a combination of a longitudinal wave together with a shear wave which, propagate with different velocities, develop, in the fiber as well as in the matrix. Since the wave velocities are different in different materials, we end up with four different wave speeds. Moreover, the amplitudes of the respective waves are varying over the cross section.

Fig. 3a: matrix crack plus debonding

Fig. 3b: extended debonding of fiber end

A further type of wave develops, namely a longitudinal wave propagating in radial direction as a consequence of lateral extension owing to the Poissons ratio. This wave is

reflected on the unbounded side faces of the specimen. Obviously, a very complex situation arises with several wave types simultaneously propagating in different directions with different wave velocities. The sensors on the faces are hit by two types of waves, by the shear wave propagating in longitudinal direction as well as by the longitudinal wave running in lateral direction.

In fig 3a, a small debonding zone is visible at the fiber ends. In this particular case two additional almost perpendicular penny shaped matrix cracks develop. In the upper half they are very close to each other so it's difficult to discriminate them. The case of pure debonding is found in fig. 3b. The fiber ends retracted in the debonded zone during the fracture process without causing a matrix crack. Figs. 3a,b show two typical patterns, however, many other crack patterns are found around fractured fibers.

ENERGY RELEASED DURING FIBER FRACTURE

The energy released during fiber fracture can be estimated by a finite element analysis. Five different scenarios are analysed, this is, a pure fiber crack without any matrix or interface damage as well as different simultaneously developing matrix or interface cracks (fig. 4). The penny shaped matrix cracks vary from a short one with a length of 1/10 of the fiber radius up to a length of one fiber radius. It has to be noted that the length of the matrix crack is measured from the fiber surface, this is, the crack front of a matrix crack of one fiber radius lies two times the fiber radius apart from the fiber center. In addition to the matrix cracks, a simultaneous interface crack of one fiber radius in length is studied.

Figure 4: Energy released by fiber break and simultaneous matrix and interface cracks

The fiber crack propagating to the fiber center causes an increasing amount of energy released. At the same time the crack area increment decreases strongly with the crack length. As result, the energy release rate increases dramatically when the crack approaches the fiber center. This means that the fiber crack is a highly unstable process, causing a high excess of energy. In case of simultaneous radial matrix cracks the released energy evidently even grows with the length of the matrix crack. However, the energy release rate is decreased due to the growing total crack area, i.e. the area of fiber

plus matrix crack. The area of the matrix crack increases (approximately) with the square of the crack length. This leads to a stop of the crack at some point. Usually, many fiber breaks can be produced without significant crack growth. An interface crack has a similar effect on the released energy, however the influence on the energy release rate is different, because the crack area grows only linear with the crack length.

CRACK VELOCITY / SAMPLING RATE

Now we come back to the wave initiated by the very fast cracking of the fiber. Gross et al [3] determined the velocity of unstable cracks in glass as well as in PMMA. Both materials behave rather brittle. They found that in both cases the crack velocity is around 45% of the velocity of a Rayleigh wave in the respective material. The Rayleigh wave velocities are about 3370 m/s in glass and 970 m/s in PMMA, that is, the velocity of an unstable crack is about 1520 m/s in glass and 440 m/s in PMMA. The crack velocity of the epoxy resin used in this paper is in the same range.

With these data we can estimate the duration of the fracture processes. Assuming that the fiber breaks axisymmetrical from the surface to the center, it needs about $2.5 \cdot 10^{-8}$ seconds. A radial matrix crack of the same length needs about $9 \cdot 10^{-8}$ seconds. The time span between two data points recorded with a sampling rate of 50 MHz is $2 \cdot 10^{-8}$ seconds. This means that even with the high sampling rate the process of a pure fiber fracture is monitored by two points maximal. This shows that we have no chance to monitor the process of fiber fracture directly. A matrix crack of same length is monitored at most by five points. It comes out that neither the breakage process of a fiber nor of the matrix crack length can be resolved sufficiently.

PURE FIBER BREAK

When a fiber, which is embedded in a matrix breaks, either a matrix crack or a debonding of the fiber end occurs simultaneously. In order to get the characteristic signal of a pure fiber break, a fiber is glued on the top surface of a cut dogbone specimen. The fiber bridges the gap between the two ends of the specimen. The two parts of the specimen are of different lengths in order to monitor the change of the signal with the distance from the source. The 3mm gap between the two parts is lying between sensor 1 and 2 with a distance of 12.5mm from sensor 1 and 9.5mm from sensor 2. The fiber broke on the right edge, next to sensor 2. The wave propagating towards sensor 1 passed the 3mm fiber bridging the gap and propagated subsequently another 12.5mm through the specimen before reaching sensor 1. Sensor 2 is reached by the wave after running 9.5mm through the specimen. The third sensor is 25mm apart from sensor 2, so the wave had passed 34.5mm in total.

In fig.5a the signals recorded by the three sensors are plotted, showing the different arrival times. From the delay of the signal between sensor 2 and 3 of about 12.5 microseconds we can determine a wave velocity of about 2000 m/s in this particular material. The free fiber part bridging the gap oscillates, which results in an additional signal, superimposed to the fiber crack (sensor 1).

Figure 5a: AE signal of pure fiber break

Figure 5b: AE signal of sensor 1

Besides the different arrival times some essential differences between the three sensors can be found. The first halfwave recorded by sensor 1 and 2 looks pretty much the same showing some oscillations with a higher frequency. The duration of the first halfwave at these sensors is about $6 \cdot 10^{-6}$ seconds, this is, much longer than the duration of the original event. By contrast, sensor 3 shows a much smoother signal with a larger wavelength. The higher frequencies are damped out. Figure 5b shows the full signal recorded by sensor 1. The diminishes largely within about 50 microseconds, revealing a high damping rate. The waveform again shows the superimposition of several oscillations

FIBER BREAK IN A MODEL COMPOSITE

Now we study the break of a fiber surrounded by matrix, this is, the fracture of a fiber in the center of the dogbone specimen. We examine two types of fiber breaks, which have different locations relative to the sensors. In one case the fiber break occurs almost in the middle between two sensors, in the second case it occurs directly at a sensor. One should, however, keep in mind that the signal still has to cross one half of the specimen width (2.5mm), since the fiber lies in the middle of the cross section.

Fiber Fracture in Model Composite - Case 1

The first case studied is the particular fiber fracture shown in the micrograph in figure 3a. The acoustic emission signals generated by this event are given in figures 6-8, with the amplitudes versus time on the left and the frequency spectra on the right. In the event under consideration, the fiber break is accompanied by a simultaneous interface crack and two penny shaped matrix cracks which are very close to each other (fig. 3a). The fiber break occurred between sensor 1 and 2, with a distance of 11mm to sensor 1, 14mm to sensor 2 and 39mm to sensor 3.

The waveform of the sensor next to the event is rather irregular, especially in the beginning, revealing that several effects are superimposed. The amplitude at sensor 2 (fig. 7a) is significantly lower than that at sensor 1 (fig 6a), even though distance to the fiber break is relatively small. In addition, the pronounced characteristics of the first halfwave of sensor 1 has almost diminished at sensor 2. Reaching sensor 3, the signal has already lost most of its intensity (fig. 8a). Not only the amplitude but also the frequency distribution suffers a large change when the wave travels through the specimen. The second

frequency maximum around 400 kHz, which is found at sensor 1 and 2 (fig 6b, 7b) has almost disappeared at sensor 3 (fig. 8b).

Figure 6a: AE signal of sensor 1

Figure 6b: Frequency spectrum of sensor 1

Figure 7a: AE signal of sensor 2

Figure 7b: Frequency spectrum of sensor 2

Figure 8a: AE signal of sensor 3

Figure 8b: Frequency spectrum of sensor 3

These results show that the signal undergoes an extensive change even over small distances. Within 25mm, which is a very small distance compared to the dimensions of structural parts, the signal loses its main characteristics. While the decrease of the amplitude between sensor 1 to sensor 2 is moderate, it is dramatic for sensor 3. The position of the break, however, can be determined by comparison of the different arrival times at the sensors with good accuracy.

Fiber Fracture in Model Composite - Case 2

We have to pay attention that in the experimental setup used in this example the positions of sensor 2 and 3 are interchanged, this is, sensor 2 is located on the right and sensor 3 is in the middle. The event takes place directly at sensor 3. The amplitude (fig. 11a) is significantly higher compared to the other sensors (figs. 9a, 10a), the frequency spectrum is pretty wide in this case (fig. 11b). As expected, both remote sensors behave almost identical concerning the amplitudes (figs. 9a, 10a) as well as the frequency spectra (figs. 9b, 10b).

Figure 9a: AE signal of sensor 1

Figure 9b: Frequency spectrum of sensor 1

Figure 10a: AE signal of sensor 2

Figure 10b: Frequency spectrum of sensor 2

Figure 11a: AE signal of sensor 3

Figure 11b: Frequency spectrum of sensor 3

Comparing this particular case with the first one discussed earlier, we see that the signal of the first event is significantly stronger. This is because the fiber broke at a higher load, causing larger damage of the matrix in the vicinity of the fiber break. The waveform of the sensors located directly at the fiber breaks in both cases do not reveal any common characteristics except of the irregularity. The frequency spectra as well do not show clear common features.

CONCLUSIONS

The experiments show that the abilities of the acoustic emission analysis to discriminate elementary failure processes are very limited. The AE analysis offers a good opportunity to localize the event if the dimensions of the specimen are moderate, i.e. several 10 millimeters. The characterization of the source by the wave form or the frequency spectrum is rather insufficient, even in very simple model composites. In particular we found that:

- acoustic emission analysis of the failure of a single fiber, embedded in dogbone specimen without using amplifiers is possible in principle
- the high damping of a polymeric matrix leads to a significant change not only of the amplitude but especially on the frequency spectrum within short distances of some ten millimeters
- if the signal is recorded by only one sensor the evaluation is very much restricted if the distance to the source is unknown
- the recorded signal rather reveals the characteristics of the specimen as well as of the sensor than of the source
- different failure processes cannot be identified satisfactory

In real composites, the wave propagation is by far more complex than in the model composite studied here, e.g. due to the large number of interfaces the wave has to cross. As a result we cannot expect to characterize single processes in a real composite material but we can only get some overall measure for the damage. However, if the intensity of the damage is large enough, we can at least localize it.

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